

Nina Cvar^{1*}, Simona Stojanova^{2*}, Jure Trilar^{3*}, Nataša Božić^{4*}, Argene Superina^{5*}

^{1*} reserach associate, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Tržaška Cesta 25, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia & assistant professor at Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana, Aškerčeva 2, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia, nina.cvar@fe.uni-lj.si & nina.cvar@ff.uni-lj.si

^{2*} resercher and a Phd candidate: Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Tržaška Cesta 25, 1000 Ljubljana, simona.stojanova@fe.uni-lj.si

^{3*} assistant researcher with Phd, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Tržaška Cesta 25, 1000 Ljubljana, jure.trilar@fe.uni-lj.si

^{4*} resercher: Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Tržaška Cesta 25, 1000 Ljubljana, natasa.bozic@fe.uni-lj.si

^{5*} resercher: Faculty of Electrical Engineering, University of Ljubljana, Tržaška Cesta 25, 1000 Ljubljana, argene.superina@fe.uni-lj.si

Title: Inclusive digital transformation for all: digital transformation of rural areas and reposition of a smart multidisciplinary methodological approach of SEROI+

Abstract: According to EUROSTAT, in 2018 about 29.1% of the EU-28 population lived in rural areas across Europe (Cvar et al. 2020) with almost 9 out of 10 predominantly rural regions in the EU (355 out of 406 regions for which data are available) reported negative crude rates of natural population change during the period 2015–2020 (EUROSTAT 2018; 2023). All in all, data show that populations living in rural areas (compared with urban areas) are facing the risk of poverty or social exclusion, and not having adequate digital skills only increases the danger of poverty. On the other hand, it is suggested that digital technologies can help rural areas to overcome these challenges. But distribution of digital technologies has never been equal as it is connected to a pattern of inequality (Rosa et al. 2013). Adoption of digital technologies is therefore related to the relation between technology and the social structure with four pertinent challenges: 1. how to assess digital maturity; 2. scattered and fragmented data with the non-existent pan-European mechanism to provide stakeholders with a much broader overview of the rural world throughout the European Union; 3. how to calculate social, economic and environmental return on investment based on publicly available indicator proxy values; 4. how to work with rural communities.

In the EU, several tools have been developed to assess digital maturity, with DESI being the most widely used. However, due to DESI shortcomings, new methodological solutions need to be developed. In rural areas, availability, access and usage of (open) data is lacking, and digital strategies often fail to address this, despite evidence showing that rural communities can significantly benefit from investments in the data economy (Data.Europa, 2024). New data approach needs to involve active engagement of (rural) communities in collecting, analysing and utilizing data to address local issues and needs. A tool that would support public and private bodies in selecting, developing and designing new products and services that respond to the needs of their communities is integral to inclusive digital transformation. Development of such a tool needs to employ an adaptation of the community-centred development approach. A descriptive review of some of the existing tools, as well as experiences and learnings from rural innovators within each of the above identified challenges, with a specific focus on introducing existing good practices, developed within EU projects (Horizon, Interreg), will be presented in this paper. In the final stages SEROI+, a tool, developed by University of Ljubljana, Nièvre Numérique and Rise Research Institutes will be presented due to its participatory, bottom-up approach, underscoring open innovation process, as well as aspiring to provide assessment and evaluation and monitoring of existing or planned products and services delivering socio-economic returns (SEROI+, 2024).

Key words: digital transformation, digital maturity, smart methodologies, data, SEROI+,

1. Introduction

According to EUROSTAT, in 2018 about 29.1% of the EU-28 population lived in rural areas across Europe (Cvar et al., 2020) with almost 9 out of 10 predominantly rural regions in the EU (355 out of 406 regions for which data are available) reported negative crude rates of natural population change during the period 2015–2020 (EUROSTAT 2018; 2023). All in all, data show that populations living in rural areas (compared with urban areas) are facing the risk of poverty or social exclusion, and not having adequate digital skills only increases the danger of poverty. On the other hand, it is suggested that digital technologies can help rural areas to overcome these challenges. But distribution of digital technologies has never been equal as it is connected to a pattern of inequality (Rosa et al., 2013). Adoption of digital technologies is therefore related to the relation between technology and the social structure with four pertinent research challenges, around which this paper will be structured:

1. how to assess digital maturity;
2. scattered and fragmented data with the non-existent pan-European mechanism to provide stakeholders with a much broader overview of the rural world throughout the European Union;
3. how to calculate social, economic and environmental return on investment based on publicly available indicator proxy values;
4. development of a SEROI+ tool, also as a result from working with rural communities.

In the EU, several tools have been developed to assess digital maturity, with DESI being the most widely used. However, due to DESI shortcomings, new methodological solutions need to be developed. In rural areas, availability, access and usage of (open) data is lacking, and digital strategies often fail to address this, despite evidence showing that rural communities can significantly benefit from investments in the data economy (Data.Europe, 2024).

New data approach needs to involve active engagement of (rural) communities in collecting, analysing and utilizing data to address local issues and needs. The central thesis of this paper argues that quantitative methods are more related to a top-down approach, while qualitative to bottom-up approach, which also functions as on the participatory bases. Although, the combination of both is important. Yet, there are at least two problems when we talk about the development of methodologies: 1. the relevance to understand the needs and, above all, the specificities of the areas we are working with, 2. in relation to the first point, how we can define a set of adequate indicators. Development of a tool that would support public and private bodies in selecting, developing and designing new products and services that respond to the needs of their communities is thus integral to inclusive digital transformation. Description of the existing tools as well as experiences and learnings from rural innovators within each of the above identified challenges, with a specific focus on introducing existing good practices, developed within EU projects (Horizon, Interreg etc.), will be presented in this paper. Although, it is important to underline, that this research will not offer revisions of the presented measurement tools – comparison of tools will be based on descriptive bases. In the concluding phase, the paper will briefly present the SEROI+ tool.

2. Inspecting key concepts: Smartness assessment methodologies, digital maturity and digital maturity assessment tools

Inclusive digital transformation is about harvesting economic and social benefits, which result from unlocking new opportunities, supporting economic growth, reducing poverty, improving public service delivery, and accelerating social inclusion in rural areas. Yet, as argued by Ferrai et al, contributions resulting from digital technologies do not only entail benefits, as they can bring possible challenges too, for instance privacy, data security, data management, lack of connectivity, new forms of social divide, the so-called digital divide (Ferrari et al., 2022). Development of a community tailored approach, understanding how to deal and manage digital transformation at the local level is crucial, especially due the importance of rural areas for Europe; according to data, more than 137 million people are living in rural communities, representing 80% of Europe's territory (Jakobsen et al., 2023).

Furthermore, these territories are indispensable in terms of local food production, sustainability of natural resources, and protection of cultural and natural heritage. Thus, acceleration of inclusive digital transformation, based on a holistic, whole-of-society approach is advised (UNDP, 2022). But what does this whole-of-society approach consist of in regard to inclusive digital transformation?

For digital transformation to be inclusive, the support framework should consider not only the needs of rural areas, but also their digital maturity. Digital maturity is broadly defined as an indicator for designing digital strategies (Brunari et al., 2022).

In rural areas, digital maturity addresses overall readiness of rural areas for digital transformation (ENRD, 2020). In relation to smartness assessment methodologies, digital maturity is mainly centered on the general readiness of rural areas for digital transformation, whereas so-called smartness methodologies are focused on evaluating effectiveness of digital technologies in achieving specific goals within rural contexts.

As claimed by Martinez-Gil et al., digital maturity is concerned more with technology adoption, whereas smartness assessment takes into consideration also other dimensions, such as social, economic, and environmental aspects (Martinez-Gil et al., 2019).

To better understand the relation between digital maturity a, genealogy of the term "smart" needs to be provided, as the term represents a key conceptual element in digital transformation of urban, as well as rural areas. Additionally, it is taken as a discursive key element for various methodologies, addressing smartness assessments. The origin of the smartness assessment concept comes from the context of smart cities which paved the way for smart villages, that, at least in EU, got popularized when the Smart Village Initiative was launched by the European Parliament in 2017, and the EU Action for Smart Villages document was published by the European Commission together with the European Parliament (Zavratnik et al., 2018). Poletini explains that "/.../ smart means using digital technologies when they are appropriate, not because they are fashionable. [...] smart means building new forms of cooperation and alliances between farmers and other rural actors; between municipalities; the private sector and civil society; from the bottom-up and the top down (Poletini, 2018: 6). Being smart in terms of digital transformation is thus not just about addressing complex problems through technology, but is also about enhancing local knowledge (Sutriadi, 2018).

Needless to say, both concepts, i.e. smartness assessment and digital maturity, are indispensable for improving quality of life in rural areas, however in this paper we are focused on reviewing existing digital maturity assessment tools, used in particular in rural areas.

2.1. Contextualization of digital maturity: from business sector to rural policies

When inspecting existing tool for assessing digital maturity, most of the tools are designed for business environments. Implementation of digital technologies is crucial for achieving

widespread economic digitalization and the efficient utilization of these technologies by companies in their operational processes is called digital maturity. In this manner, digital maturity serves as a measurement of a company's or country's advancement in implementing and using digital technologies to accomplish their goals (Calabrese, Levialedi Ghiron & Tiburzi, 2021).

Achieved levels constantly evolve with the emergence of new technologies and automation systems, implying changes on the companies' business models (Bleicher & Stanley, 2017). Unique characteristics of rural business landscapes also contribute to this scenario. It can be anticipated that small businesses in rural areas will tailor their strategies to suit the demands of their local business environments when adopting new (digital) technologies. Consequently, they may not inherently be less innovative than their urban counterparts; rather, they often exhibit differences in terms of their business models and technology adoption practices (Fanelli, 2021). For instance, small enterprises in rural regions frequently prioritize local markets and engage in locally oriented trade, which could explain their relatively lower utilization of digital business models like e-commerce or internet platforms (Galloway, Sanders & Deakins, 2011).

The increasing importance of convenient access to online services for ordinary citizens, emphasizing its necessity rather than just a luxury, has been recognized years back by Roberts et al. (Roberts et al., 2017) arguing that individuals lacking Internet access and digital skills results in social exclusion, which leads to digital exclusion, perpetuating a cycle of inequality. This phenomenon operates globally, regionally, and locally, impacting both urban and rural areas. Communities undergo ongoing change from various sources. This ability of individuals and communities to actively adjust to ongoing changes by enhancing their capacity and resources is called resilience (Magis, 2010).

Digital technologies have an impact on community resilience by the potential of creating economic opportunities and with this empowering individual, and communities (Mehen, 2023). However, communities must wisely choose the digital advancements, their benefit and risks ensuring sustainable development (Mehan & Mostafavi, 2022).

Yet, these digital advancements, which need to be based on inclusivity, are very much dependent on the ability of data.

3. Mapping existing digital maturity assessment tools

3.1. Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI)

One of the first steps that policy makers take, when they start working on a specific issue, related to digital transformation, is conducting analysis via The Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI). DESI measures digital transformation of businesses, infrastructure deployment, digital skills of human capital and e-government services (Mreža NVO-VID, 2021). Nevertheless, DESI is limited due to several reasons: it misses different aspects of the quality of life in the digital societies of the EU Member States, such as digital rights, accessibility, trust in digital technologies, multi-stakeholder participation, etc. (ibid.). Besides, DESI does not measure the development of the digital society in terms of ensuring a safe, secure, solidarity-based, fair, sustainable and open digital environment (ibid.). But perhaps the most pertinent is its limitation when assessing digital maturity of rural areas, with urban bias being detected as well. In reference to EPRI, DESI has difficulty in demonstrating unique challenges, related to infrastructure, connectivity, adoption of digital technologies and access to digital skills and competences (EPRI, 2020).

To encapsulate, according to EPRI, DESI is too standardized, meaning that its metrics may not be able to fully capture nuances of rural areas (ibid.). Thus, DESI should be complemented by other, more customized tools, that consider unique traits of rural areas. If possible, development of tools should draw on direct experience on the ground.

3.2. Territorial digital assessment tool

Territorial digital assessment tool is assessing digital maturity of territories, including remote and peripheral areas. This free for use tool is intended for public, private, or community stakeholders who wish to assess the digital maturity of their territories, with the purpose of identifying and addressing key challenges of digital transformation, based on which they can reshape and enhance their digital transformation strategies. The tool was developed within the framework of the Interreg Europe CARPE DIGEM project, co-financed by the European Regional Development Fund. The tool consists of nine key dimensions that are related to both preconditions and accelerators of digital transformation of territories. Dimensions assessed are infrastructure, open data, digital education, attraction and retention of talent from the field of IT, digital competences of companies, digital innovation ecosystems, finance, support services and governance and leadership (carpedigem.eu, 2024). For each dimension a scoring system from 1 – 5 will was developed to indicate the current state of play. The tool generates a report, consisting of visual diagram, accompanied with achieved levels of digital maturity for each of the listed dimension.

3.3. Digital Maturity Check – CORA

Within the scope of Interreg North Sea project CORA (connecting remote areas with digital infrastructure and services) the challenge of measuring digital maturity of small municipalities and rural areas was addressed through the maturity analysis model, which aimed to provide a simple and intuitive tool to support these entities on their digital transformation journey. Maturity assessment enables a quick overview of overall digital readiness of small municipalities and rural areas and provides a possibility to accurately identify priority areas where further investments and development are necessary.

The tool covers the following four broad aspects of digitalization: organization, competencies, technologies and strategies (ruraldigital.eu, 2024).

Compared to the Territorial digital assessment tool, Digital maturity check – Cora is focused on municipalities, generating similar type report in terms of identification of strengths and potential gaps. It is free for use, as other previously listed tools.

3.4. Digital maturity assessment tool for regions and cities – LORDIMAS

During October and November 2023 Living-in.EU introduced for the first time a digital maturity assessment tool for regions and cities – LORDIMAS, which was developed by ESPON in cooperation with the European Committee of the Regions, European Commission and Living-in.EU. LORDIMAS is a free and interactive tool which introduces seven sections as categories of the digital landscape (governance, service design, data management, interoperability, service delivery, technology and networking) and were decided upon based on 29 different regional and local indicators (gis-portal.espon.eu, 2024). This tool provides data managers and local governments an opportunity to evaluate their level of digital maturity and obtain valuable insights. What makes this tool particularly interesting is the fact that it is dynamic,

meaning that it allows authorities to review and update their data to keep it current with the ever-changing demands and difficulties. LORDIMAS encourages cooperation, benchmarking, and data exchange between local and regional government agencies. With this process it contributes to advancing open data initiatives across EU and gives users the ability to actualize their full digital potential, share knowledge and act towards more effective governance (Data Europe, 2024).

3.5. DVI Readiness Assessment Tool

In 2021, FAO (Food and Agriculture Organisation of United Nations) launched the Digital Villages Initiative (DVI), with the aim of transforming at least 1000 villages worldwide into Digital Villages. The initiative acknowledges both the potential risks and the opportunities presented by ICT, and was created in order to help accelerate the transformation of agri-food systems and advance the Sustainable Development Goals. Through DVI, FAO is assisting rural digital transformation process aimed at addressing the issues agri-food systems are facing and enhancing the resilience and standard of living of rural populations. DVI addresses three key dimensions: firstly, it aims to boost agricultural productivity through the implementation of "smart farming solutions," leveraging internet-connected devices like sensors, drones, and agrobots, along with digital technologies such as IoT, AI, and remote sensing, to optimize farming practices for precision, automation, and sustainability. Secondly, it seeks to improve farmers' access to digital services, including advisory, financial, insurance, and social protection services, while enhancing connectivity to markets and suppliers to improve the efficiency of food value chains. Finally, DVI supports a comprehensive digital transformation of rural communities by enhancing public service delivery across sectors like health, education, tourism, transportation, and energy, while also fostering digital skills, community initiatives, and partnerships to drive innovation and co-creation (openknowledge.fao.org, 2024). The tool analyses the level of maturity of potential digital villages across 17 criteria in 3 dimensions: digital ecosystems, leadership and governance, and strategic context. Each criterion is assigned a score ranging from 1 to 5, culminating in a final score that indicates the community's overall readiness to partake in the DVI transformation process.

Table: List of presented tools

Tool name	Short description	Dimensions measuring for	End users	Source
Territorial digital assessment tool	A tool for measuring the digital maturity of territories, including remote and peripheral areas.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -infrastructure -open data -digital education -attraction and retention of IT talent -digital competences of companies -digital innovation ecosystems -finance -support services 	Public, private and community stakeholders	https://carpedigem.eu/tool/?lan=en

		-governance and leadership		
Digital Maturity Check - CORA	Tool enables a quick overview of overall digital readiness of small municipalities and rural areas and provides a possibility to accurately identify priority areas where further investments and development are crucial.	-organization -competences -technologies -strategies	Local authorities	https://ruraldigital.eu/heck-your-digital-maturity-2/
Digital maturity assessment tool for regions and cities – LORDIMAS	LORDIMAS encourages cooperation, benchmarking, and data exchange between local and regional government agencies. Tool aims at advancing open data initiatives across EU, knowledge sharing and acting towards more effective governance.	-governance -service design -data management -interoperability -service delivery -technology -networking	Data managers and local and regional authorities	https://gis-portal.espon.eu/arcgis/apps/experiencebuilder/experience/?id=975e0dd3bcf84aa9810f05b5f7b9b65&page=page_13&views=view_104
DVI Readiness Assessment Tool	An instrument for evaluating a rural community's preparedness to embark on a Digital Village transformation journey.	-digital ecosystems -strategic context -leadership and governance	Farmers, agri-food systems, rural communities	https://forms.office.com/pages/responsepage.aspx?id=aMQ6Frir0ESB_dnbFeOvlhwrEn_dEeEtBhK6IKASp4fVUM0Q3V1dFNkY2RF_EwQIIIQ0RISFcxRzRMWC4u

4. What data sources to use: challenges and future prospects

4.1. Top-down framework

Obtaining data and moreover obtaining quality data is a big challenge when working in rural areas. Therefore, efficient data approach needs to involve active engagement of (rural) communities in collecting, analysing and utilizing data to address local issues and needs. The European Union's Data Strategy, introduced in 2020, seeks to turn Europe into a leading model of a society empowered by data, facilitating better decision-making in both business and the public sector (Weber, 2023).

Approaching from the top-down overview of strategic EU frameworks to provide legal outlines on innovative technologies with some of the current directives and regulations from several perspectives according to Weber are the following: 1) Data Use, such as European Data Governance Act, Digital Markets Act, Digital Services Act Regulation, Data Act; 2) Data

Protection and; 3) Data Security, both exhibited in General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) with its Article 32; 4) Data Quality, connected to the new AI Act; 5) Sustainability and Ethics, in AI Act as well as other environmental, social and governance regulation and corporate social responsibility guidelines alongside with existing national legal frameworks of Member States (ibid.).

The multitude of data governance rules that affect the European Data Ecosystems can already be recognized. All these regulations are reflected in operational and practical (ISO, EN) standards and technical architecture frameworks, e.g. Gaia-X, a federated secure data infrastructure, and Fiware and policy rules on common EU Data Spaces (Otto et al., 2022b). Apart from the definitive legislative harmonization and operational and technical standardization efforts that shape the semantic vocabulary and data ecosystems in Europe, the actual data useful in the assessments and policy design tools for rural development is discovered from numerous global, international, national and local “data suppliers”.

Most important ready-to-use data-set sources within public sector would include sources from Eurostat, ESPON, OECD, National Statistical Centers, Copernicus programme, World Health Organisation, World Bank, and national ministries, play a crucial role in providing statistical data for analysis (Mensah & Goderre, 2020; Mustapa et al., 2022; Lassinati, 2014).

Most relevant for the development of SEROI+ tool were World bank indicators that offer global comparisons and opportunities for quantitative decision support tools in-between different scope of geographical areas involved in related analyses. Further, data sets, usable for geo-spatial and statistical analyses of rural contexts emerge outside the publicly governed institutions and envelop public participatory approaches, e.g. Open Street Map, or commercial interests, e.g. Google and navigation services providers

As an example, data-sets from infrastructure services providers can present great opportunities within regional and spatial data and analyses, as demonstrated by University of Oulu within Horizon project SMART community-led transition for Europe’s Rural Areas (<https://smartera-project.eu/>, 2024).

Multi-dimensional analyses of data sets retrieved from mobile telco providers investigate the smartness and socio-economic dynamics in rural areas for inter/intra-regional mobility patterns, accessibility of services (4/5G and fiber networks) and rural population concentration and changes including migration and seasonal populations.

The existing challenges in the European rural sector stem from scattered and fragmented data, coupled with the absence of a pan-European mechanism to offer stakeholders a comprehensive view of rural landscapes (Charvat et al., 2014; Marino & Tebala, 2022; Kusio & Fiore, 2022). The lack of cohesive data sources inhibits in-depth analyses and hinders effective comparisons between urban and rural areas. This data fragmentation also restricts the ability to evaluate policy performance comprehensively, especially in terms of less tangible aspects.

4.2. Data readiness and identification of a mixed-method approach: data-sets, data sources and community-centered development approach

To address these limitations, a mixed-method approach combining spatial econometrics, stakeholder analysis, and qualitative interviews is proposed to enhance policy evaluation and management by providing a more holistic understanding of the multifaceted determinants of policy performance.

Apart from verified and relevant “external” data sources, actionable considerations deriving from regional or local territory assessment and planning tools must be pertinent to local features, economy and community’s needs and requirements. Efforts to bridge these data

gaps and establish more integrated assessment tools are crucial for planning sustainable rural development and fostering informed decisions across various stakeholder groups. This knowledge discovery, embodied in the term data readiness (Klievink, 2016) encompasses more than just data availability; it involves ensuring that data meets specific requirements for immediate analysis (Douthit. et al, 2021). Authors of this article acknowledge that data readiness also involves the capacity to create new data sets, in the case of rural development, in the spaces and communities where it is traditionally lacking.

These data-sets can be retrieved from data repositories collecting data from local sensor infrastructure which aside from usual weather-related data can integrate very diverse use cases, e.g. real-time of historic data from wine growing process (Smart Agro Grape project) and beekeeping data to monitor beehive behaviour patterns (Horizon Europe CODECS project).

Community engagement in data decision making within and for communities in rural areas is of great importance. Data can help communities target community relevant interventions and measure progress, which is necessary to pave the way for a prosperous, sustainable and more equitable future for all (Crawford et al, 2023). While paramount, key inputs from working with communities can be retrieved via plethora of open science, open innovation, community engagement methods and activities in building regional/local stakeholder groups, some, especially important for assessment of existing services can be obtained with usage data of local digital solutions using user interfaces interactions or AI chatbot query data.

Among other objectives, SEROI+ aims to provide an approach towards meaningful analysis of data that are available in rural (European) topology and range from publicly available statistical data, automatically retrieved data from sensors as well as inputs collected from the local community. The authors are aware that the range of data sources, it's veracity in volume and velocity, pose a (statistical) methodology risk, yet recognise the need for such tool for usage in special geographical and other contexts, to provide with relevant, legitimate, actionable and authentic assessments in a world where typically on-demand complete data-sets are now available.

5. Working with rural communities

Work with rural communities could be divided into two directions: the first, how to work with the communities, whereas the second is how the communities themselves are addressing the challenge of digital transformation. In our previous work, we have underlined the importance of place-based and context-based approach, which underscores community actions and strengthens local democracy (Zavratnik et al., 2019; Cvar et al. 2020; Stojanova et al. 2022). Bellefontaine et al. is for instance arguing, that a place-based approach targets unique conditions of specific environments, stipulating collaborative decision-making processes, sharing initiative, fostering local talents, resources, and stakeholder interests (Bellefontaine et al., 2020). Even though they are different concepts, how to work on rural community engagement: from smart villages, living labs to rural hubs, all these approaches need to be supported by policy makers and other relevant stakeholders. In these terms, a well-thought strategic and participatory process is needed to assure a comprehensive plan that guides their development activities. It is the latter that encouraged us to develop a tool, that would provide to a heterogenous group of stakeholders, e.g. local communities, business, educators etc. to evaluate different investment strategies, and their financial implications, with consideration to the social and environmental aspects too, but considering participatory, open innovation practice as well. A network of these various reasons encouraged us to start working on developing with our long-term partners the so-called SEROI+ tool.

6. Case study: SEROI+

6.1. Definition

SEROI+ stands for social, economic, environmental return on investment with open innovation. SEROI+ methodology supports public and private bodies in selecting, developing, and designing new products and services that respond to the needs of their communities.

Open innovation (OI) is a process that enables public or private entities to involve all relevant stakeholders in identification and definition of goals and objectives, identification of measurable indicators and expected impacts, and in co-design and co-development of new products and services (SEROI+, 2024).

6.2. Context and development

High Speed Broadband is a key factor in helping rural areas in Europe develop and sustain their economies and communities. Between 2012 and 2014 the Interreg IVC ENGAGE project partners worked together to develop a series of resources, tools and strategies to enable High Speed Broadband networks to be developed at efficient cost, translating their best practices into effective and efficient policies to help all of rural Europe be better connected. Following three years of collaboration and exchange between the ENGAGE partnership and institutions at European, national, regional and local levels we have produced a series of practical recommendations appropriate for all European regions and a series of tools and instruments to inform or inspire other regions across Europe on the practicalities, opportunities and benefits offered by High Speed Broadband.

The project partners have continued to consider how to justify the investment in High Speed Broadband and make this infrastructure as useful and tailored as possible to the needs of end-users living in rural Europe. Activities continued with the support of the new Interreg Europe project "Enhancing Rural and Urban Digital Innovation Territories (ERUDITE)" in 2016 – 2020.

When the project began in 2016 all the partners in ERUDITE had successfully extended High Speed Broadband infrastructure to reach a significant number of urban and rural communities in their regions and enable all stakeholders to contribute and benefit from the digital economy and society.

To fully exploit the economic and social potential of these networks new services needed to be designed to meet public, private and community needs and justify public investments in infrastructure and uses. To achieve these aims the project undertook the design of new services supported by open innovation processes involving and empowering businesses, citizens, and public administrations, thereby stimulating demand and local innovation capacity potential, enabling stakeholders to be partners in the creation and operation of services that improve territorial potential. To increase understanding of the design, operation and impacts of services, the open innovation process was supported by social and economic return on investment (SEROI) studies providing data to illustrate global social and economic impacts and support more targeted investments.

ERUDITE partners have concluded that the development, design, and implementation of effective digital services in Europe requires an innovative rethinking of the process. Several workshops across Europe were used to develop, test and improve a so called SEROI+ methodology that guides us through key stages in just 4 steps:

1. Defining goals (define policy or practice goals for the services);

2. Stakeholder mapping (identify and engage relevant stakeholders and define their goals);
3. Co-design the service;
4. Measuring the value (set indicators and values, estimate and then monitor social, economic, and environmental return on investment).

University of Ljubljana has developed a web tool for the first three steps of the methodology to continue working with communities in rural areas (seroi.plus, 2024).

6.3. Follow-up

In 2021 – 2022 a follow-up of the ERUDITE project was approved. COVID-19 accelerated the use, visibility and diffusion of digital tools and services in rural areas. Confinement measures encouraged a long-term move to remote working, learning and e-services. This was of particular importance in rural and peripheral regions. 8 ERUDITE partners continued with an exchange programme to evaluate the impact of the crisis on the development and operation of digital services and developed measures to respond. One of the results was development of prototype of SEROI+ Calculator, a digital tool to measure the value of digital services considering social, environmental, and economic impacts.

After the end of the project University of Ljubljana (Slovenia), RI:SE (Sweden) and Digital Nièvre Joint Authority (France) continued with development of the calculator tool: (impact.seroi.plus, 2024); currently, by including ML too.

6.4. Conceptual framework for the development of the SEROI+ calculator:

how to calculate social, economic and environmental return on investment based on publicly available indicator proxy values?

The so-called planning phase of any project usually involves evaluating different investment strategies to meet predetermined goals. Typically, the assessment focuses on the financial implications of each strategy, with little consideration given to the social and environmental impacts (Bohmholdt, 2014).

Return on Investments (ROI) is commonly perceived as a comparative measure of a company's achievement. It is computed to assess companies against one another within a specific industry and to evaluate their individual performance over time (Lingane & Olsen, 2004). With the shift towards the importance of social and environmental implications, the term social return on investment (SROI) analysis started to appear in the literature. The SROI framework originated from the work of the Roberts Enterprise Development Fund (Emerson & Cabaj, 2000), followed by ongoing revisions to the original methodology (Tuan, 2008). These modifications have involved integrating the initial SROI approach, assessment of the social impact, utilizing economic evaluations (Rotheroe & Richards, 2007). This approach is nowadays commonly known as the "triple bottom line". It is a quantitative approach that covers all three pillars of sustainability, environmental, economic and social impacts of current and future investments. SROI can be used as a decision-making tool. The essential steps of the SROI analysis involve identifying relevant impacts, utilizing economic techniques to quantify the social and environmental impacts, constructing the model, and evaluating the outcomes. (Bohmholdt, 2014).

Similar to a benefit-cost analysis, SROI evaluates, whether an entity benefits from taking a particular action compared to maintaining the status quo. The SROI process begins with defining project objectives and desired outcomes, as well as the main stakeholders involved. Then, potential investment strategies are identified to achieve these objectives. Next, economic, social, and environmental impacts are identified for each investment strategy, and incremental impacts are determined by comparing them to the baseline. These impacts may fluctuate over time. A life-cycle assessment is conducted to quantify the social and environmental impacts, while a life-cycle cost analysis monetizes the economic impacts. Both assessments cover the project's lifespan or a specific timeframe. Next step is to add value to each indicator, and for those who do not have a direct financial value, are assigned with financial proxies, which represent estimations of a value. In the next step, the deadweight, displacement, attribution, and the drop-off are calculated. In the last stage, the SROI (ratio) is calculated.

In the literature, there is a debate on various disadvantages of this methodology. The issue of indicators and their assigned proxy values are most commonly found in the literature. This includes challenges with choosing the indicators and access to good quality data, as well as the measurement level of the soft aspects. This further leads to constraints of replications and comparability (Maldonado & Corbey, 2016).

Following the SROI methodology, a SEROI Plus calculator was developed which represents a user-friendly tool which helps in the calculations of the return on future investments, incorporating environmental, economic, and social factors.

6.5. How the SEROI Plus calculator works?

SEROI calculator was developed because we wanted to better understand the value we are making with a specific project or service. For example: If we were talking about „remote working“, we were also talking about certain outcomes like „less cars on the roads“, „lower carbon footprint“, „lower transport expenses“, „more free time for volunteering etc.

The question was, how can we use this information, how can we calculate all those outcomes to present them in a monetary value, in Euro for example.

In addition, we wanted to evaluate the project on a stakeholder level – so that each stakeholder could easily see what's in it for them.

SEROI calculator is a web tool that is powered by a curated dataset of social, environmental, and economic outcomes. All the outcomes in the database are expressed with a measurable proxy indicators and well documented sources.

Assigned monetary values are assigned to expected outcomes. For example, we replace hard-to-measure indicators such as volunteer work with appropriate value from the existing information, which in this case would be 15 EUR per hour. This means that we assign a monetary value of 15 EUR for every hour volunteered. This proxy value allows us to represent the social impact in monetary terms, making it easier to incorporate it into the calculations.

To make sure the tool is trustworthy, source trackability is assured by examining from where and from which time-period the values emerged. This means that every proxy value that is used in the calculation has a well-documented source behind it.

Finally, the output of this calculation is an estimation of the return on investment, including social, environmental, and economic outcomes on the project, or per-stakeholder level. The calculator estimates SEROI coefficient for up to five years in advance.

7. Conclusion

Changes associated with the digital transformation process encompass various economic, political, and social spheres, including personal life (Ashrafi & Mueller, 2015). The policy agenda involves addressing specific challenges and opportunities present in rural areas for individuals, businesses, and local governments (Roberts et al., 2014). The emergence of Smart Villages has sparked various approaches for their digital advancement across societal, economic, and environmental domains. The ongoing technological development presents opportunities for future innovation, underscoring crucial role of digitalization in sustainable development. However, realizing the full potential of digital technologies necessitates robust digital cooperation and engagement between researchers and policymakers. The diverse nature of region complicates the establishment and adherence to unified rules, posing a challenge for policymakers. Nevertheless, effective collaboration between policymakers and stakeholders is imperative. Policymakers must be involved in all stages, from infrastructure establishment to digital skills development in ever aging digital technologies to address rural challenges and bridge the digital divide. Advocating for policies and implementing concrete actions will empower rural communities, fostering strength and resilience (Stojanova et al., 2022) and furthermore, encourage inclusive digital transformation.

In this paper, we have presented some of the key concepts, related to digital transformation in rural areas: digital maturity, smartness assessment and methodologies etc. But we have also tackled the issue of efficient data approach as smart use of data is fundamental for all the stakeholders involved, or better still for rural communities. Digital maturity tools listed above are certainly of tremendous help, when further steps are taken within the process of digital transformation. However, with the development of the SEROI+ tool we wanted to add to existing solutions an element of the participatory open innovation, that pursues community-centred development approach, but at the same time offers effective planning, together by providing an estimation of the return on investment, including social, environmental, and economic outcomes on the project, or per-stakeholder level.

References

- Ashrafi, R., & Mueller, J. (2015) 'Delineating IT resources and capabilities to obtain competitive advantage and improve firm performance,' *Information Systems Management*, 32(1), 15-38.
- Bellefontaine, T.; Wisener, R. The Evaluation of Place-Based Approaches: Questions for Further Research. Policy Horizons Canada, available online: <https://ccednet-rcdec.ca/en/toolbox/evaluation-place-based-approaches-questions-further-research> (accessed on 15 February 2020)
- Bleicher, J., & Stanley, H. (2017) 'Digitization as a catalyst for business model innovation a three-step approach to facilitating economic success,' *Journal of Business Management*, 12.
- Bohmholdt, A. (2019) 'Evaluating the Triple Bottom Line Using Sustainable Return on Investment,' *Remediation Journal*, 24(4), pp.53-64.
- Brunori, G., Rolandi, S., Arcuri, S. (2022) 'Digitalisation of Rural Areas. SHERPA Discussion Paper, available on: DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6421292 (accessed on 15 May 2024)
- Calabrese, A., Levialdi Ghiron, N., & Tiburzi, L. (2021) 'Evolutions' and 'revolutions' in manufacturers' implementation of industry 4.0: a literature review, a multiple case study, and a conceptual framework. *Production Planning & Control*, 32(3), 213-227

CARPE DIGEM, available online: <https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/carpedigem/> (accessed 15 May 2024)

Charvat, K., Esbri, M. A., Mayer, W., Charvat, K., Campos, A., Palma, R., & Krivanek, Z. (2014) 'Foodie — open data for agriculture' IST-Africa Conference Proceedings.

Cvar, N., Trilar, J., Kos, A., Volk, M. and Stojmenova Duh, E. (2020) 'The Use of IoT Technology in Smart Cities and Smart Villages: Similarities, Differences, and Future Prospects,' *Sensors*, 20(14), p.3897

Crawford, M., Flores, F., Kolak, M., Nelson, A. H., & Simmons, M. (2023) 'Importance of community engagement in Data Decision making,' *Big Data* 11(2), 75-86.

Data.Europe, available on: <https://data.europa.eu/en/publications/datastories/open-rural-data-gap> (accessed 15 May 2024)

Douthit, B.J., Del Fiol, G., Staes, C.J., Docherty, S.L. and Richesson, R.L. (2021) 'A Conceptual Framework of Data Readiness: The Contextual Intersection of Quality, Availability, Interoperability, and Provenance,' *Applied Clinical Informatics*, 12(03), pp.675-685.

Digital maturity assessment tool for regions and cities – LORDIMAS, available on: https://gis-portal.espon.eu/arcgis/apps/experiencebuilder/experience/?id=975e0dd3bcf84aa9810f0f5b5f7b9b65&page=page_13&views=view_104 (accessed on 15 May 2024)

Digital Maturity Check – CORA, available online: <https://ruraldigital.eu/check-your-digital-maturity-2/> (accessed on 15 May 2024)

DVI Readiness Assessment Tool, available online: https://forms.office.com/pages/responsepage.aspx?id=aMQ6Frir0ESB_dnbFeOvlhwrEndEeEtBhK6IKASp4fVUM0Q3V1dFNkY2RFEwQIIIQ0RISFcxRzRMWC4u (accessed 15 May 2024)

Emerson, J. and Cabaj, M. (2000), 'Social Return On Investment,' *auspace.athabascau.ca*, [online] Volume 11 Number 2 10-14(2), available online: <https://auspace.athabascau.ca/handle/2149/1028> (accessed on 15 May 2024)

ERUDITE, available online: <https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/erudite/> (accessed 15 May 2024)

ENRD, available online: https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publication/2023-05/smart_villages_briefs-smart_villages_and_rural_digital_transformation-v07.pdf (accessed on 15 May 2024)

EPRI, available online: <https://rural-innovation.eu/digital-economy-and-society-index-rural-areas/> (accessed on 15 May 2024)

EUROSTAT, available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/-/EDN-20200207-1> (accessed on 9 May 2020) & (accessed on 30 January 2024)

Fanelli, R. M. (2021) 'Barriers to adopting new technologies within rural small and medium enterprises (SMEs),' *Social sciences*, 10(11), 430.

Ferrari, A., Bacco, M., Gaber, K., Jedlitschka, A., Hess, S., Kaipainen, J., ... & Brunori, G. (2022), 'Drivers, barriers and impacts of digitalisation in rural areas from the viewpoint of experts,' *Information and Software Technology*, 106816

Galloway, L., Sanders, J., & Deakins, D. (2011) 'Rural small firms' use of the internet: From global to local,' *Journal of Rural Studies*, 27(3), 254-262.

Horizon CODECS, available online: <https://www.horizoncodecs.eu/> (accessed 15 May 2024)

Horizon SMART ERA, available online: <https://smartera-project.eu/> (accessed 15 May 2024)

- Jakobsen, K., Mikalsen, M. and Lilleng, G. (2023) 'A literature review of smart technology domains with implications for research on smart rural communities,' *Technology in Society*, [online] 75(75), p.102397
- Klievink, B., Romijn, B.-J., Cunningham, S., & de Bruijn, H. (2016) 'Big Data in the public sector: Uncertainties and Readiness,' *Information Systems Frontiers*, 19(2), 267-283.
- Kusio, T., & Fiore, M. (2022) 'Which stakeholders' sector matters in rural development? that is the problem' *Energies*, 15(2), 454
- Lingane, A. and Olsen, S. (2004) 'Guidelines for Social Return on Investment,' *California Management Review*, 46(3), pp.116-135.
- Magis, K. (2010) 'Community resilience: An indicator of social sustainability,' *Society and natural resources*, 23(5), 401-416.
- Maldonado, M. and Corbey, M. (2016) 'Social Return on Investment (SROI): a review of the technique' *Maandblad Voor Accountancy en Bedrijfseconomie*, 90(3), pp.79-86
- Marino, D., & Tebala, D. (2022) 'Rural Areas and Well-Being: Empirical Models and Policies', available online: <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202211.0207.v1> (accessed on 15 May 2024)
- Mehan, A., Mostafavi, S. (2022) 'Building Resilient Communities Over Time,' *The Palgrave Encyclopedia of Urban and Regional Futures*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- Mensah, E., & Goderre, J. L. (2020) 'Data sources and data tools: Preparing for the open data ecosystem,' *Health Informatics*, 105-127
- Martinez-Gil, J. et al. (2019) 'Framework for Assessing the Smartness Maturity Level of Villages,' Welzer, T., et al. *New Trends in Databases and Information Systems. ADBIS 2019. Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol 1064. Springer, Cham.
- Mreža nevladnih organizacij za vključujočo informacijsko družbo (NVO-VID), available online: <https://www.informacijska-druzba.org/2022/07/28/indeks-desi-ni-ustrezen-pokazatelj-razvitosti-digitalne-druzbe/> (accessed 15 May 2024)
- Mustapa, M. N., Hamid, S., & Md Nasaruddin, F. H. (2022) 'Factors influencing open government data post-adoption in the public sector: The perspective of Data Providers,' *PLOS ONE*, 17(11)
- openknowledge.fao.org, 2024, (accessed 15 May 2024)
- Otto, B., Hompel, T. M., & Wrobel, S. (2022), *Designing data spaces: The Ecosystem Approach to competitive advantage*, New York: Springer.
- Polettini, F. (2018) *Smartness assessment of rural areas: multicriteria rating with alpine stakeholder*, MA, available online: <https://www.politesi.polimi.it/handle/10589/146475?mode=complete> (last accessed 15 May 2024)
- Roberts, E., Anderson, B. A., Skerratt, S., & Farrington, J. (2017). A review of the rural-digital policy agenda from a community resilience perspective. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 54, 372-385
- Rotheroe, N., & Richards, A. (2007) 'Social return on investment and social enterprise: transparent accountability for sustainable development,' *Social Enterprise Journal*, 3(1), 31-48.
- Rosa, F.R.; da Silveira, S.A.; Silva, A.J.C.; Pautassi, L.; Burt, J.M.; Cagley, C.; Viegas e Silva, M.; Gilbert, J.; Timo, P.B.; Maués, A.M.; et al. (2013) 'Digital Inclusion as Public Policy' *Sur. File Inf. Hum. Rights* 10, 32-53
- ruraldigital.eu, 2024 (accessed 15 May 2024)
- SEROI+, available online: <https://seroi.plus/> (accessed 15 May 2024)

SEROI+ Calculator, available online: <http://impact.seroi.plus/> (accessed on 15 May 2024)

SMART AGRO GRAPE, available online: <https://smartagrogrape.si/> (last accessed 15 May 2024)

Stojanova, S., Cvar, N., Verhovnik, J., Božić, N., Trilar, J., Kos, A. and Stojmenova Duh, E. (2022) 'Rural Digital Innovation Hubs as a Paradigm for Sustainable Business Models in Europe's Rural Areas', *Sustainability*, [online] 14(21), p.14620

Sutriadi, R. (2018) 'Defining smart city, smart region, smart village, and technopolis as an innovative concept in Indonesia's urban and regional development themes to reach sustainability' *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.* 202, 012047

Territorial digital assessment tool, available online: <https://carpedigem.eu/tool/?lan=en> (accessed 15 May 2024)

Tuan, M.T. (2008) 'MEASURING AND/OR ESTIMATING SOCIAL VALUE CREATION: Insights Into Eight Integrated Cost Approaches Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation Impact Planning and Improvement' [online], available online: <https://docs.gatesfoundation.org/Documents/wwl-report-measuring-estimating-social-value-creation.pdf> (accessed 15 May 2024)

UNDP - Chief Digital Office (2022). *Inclusive by Design: Accelerating Digital Transformation for the Global Goals*, New York: Policy Brief

Weber, Beatrix (2023) *Data governance*, Berlin: Springer

Zavratnik, V.; Kos, A.; Stojmenova Duh, 2018 'Smart Villages: Comprehensive Review of Initiatives and Practices,' *Sustainability* 2018, 10, 2559